

MESONET LIVE DATA ACCESS

Delivering real-time weather data across Hawai'i and American Samoa

Key Features:

- ✓ Data access to 100+ weather stations
- ✓ Real-time and historical data and graphs
- ✓ Download instantly

Instantly explore real-time data or retrieve years of archived records. Designed for everyone – from emergency responders to educators – with user-friendly tools and 24/7 access.